

THE IMPACT OF DIGITAL LIBRARY SERVICES ON PUBLIC LIBRARIES

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Abstract:

The importance of digital library services in today's information age is undeniable. Providing online and digitized information is a practical step to keep up with the abundance of computer usage and the coexistence of the Internet. Needless to say, public libraries are currently on this path. Therefore, in order to judge the improvement of public libraries, it is very important to analyze the quality and usability of digital library resources and digital library services in the current situation, which indicates the impact of digital library services on public libraries.

Key Words: Public Library, Digital Library Services, Digital Library Resources, Digital Age & ICT

Introduction:

In the current era of information exploration, a huge amount of information is coming. In addition to hard copy, this repository is also increasing the amount of soft copy. As a result, libraries have become accustomed to using new advanced technology for storing and providing information. On the one hand, it has increased the area and scope of the library, on the other hand, it has also increased the level of providing library facilities to the user through the use of information communication technology. Now public libraries have no boundaries regarding time, space, racial discrimination, area. Thus, current public libraries have been able to provide anyone with any information cheaply, easily and quickly.

Thought of Topic:

Public libraries with current advanced and advanced technology are able to provide digital information through advanced devices such as computers. The current advanced library services are- Electronic journal support service, Electronic document delivery, Electronic publishing, Resource service, Inter library loan, Full text searching, Cross-searching, Specialist abstracting, Indexing databases etc. On the other hand, in today's advanced society, everyone is deeply involved in technology, especially computers, and all people are time-saving in nature. In everyday life, all tasks require the right amount of information at the right time and it can be related to any workplace like Govt. Office, Private Sector, Business, Academic Sector, Social Sector etc. Thus, public libraries connect information stored on their computers to their targeted users' personal computers via the Internet.

Literature Review:

Electronic library services are the main subject in modern academic libraries like study center libraries. Students-teachers are all interested in online documents, e-book, e-journal, e-database. And all the information will be readily available via internet and through ICT. (1)

Improvement of academic libraries is depends on use of ICT. Electronic publishing, e-main message these are the new approach to serve the users by academic libraries. ICT helps to serve library resources very easily, at the time and everywhere. (3)

Nowadays, academic study and research are moving by E-resource through computer and internet. Electronic library resources like E-books, E-journal. E-bulletin, newsletter etc. are readily available though electronic services like OPAC, E-mail service, CD-Rom database service etc. (4)

Therefore, it can be said that various electronic resources and services are the future of modern academic sector. Though modern study is more fast and technology base then their needed information will also be technology oriented and updated.

Modern libraries including public and academic all are trying to cope with digitized form both from collection development and service sector. Libraries are trying to use ICT to develop their future perspective. (2) Today's E-learning method through websites, blogs, wikis, e-mails is very much accepted by society. Library services are now come up with their digitized resources for serving their users and trying to sustain in this field. (5)

Digital library concept is a new concept for library field. Beyond the four walls and use of internet with digitized document services can be made by the library to their modern users even to the remote area. It is well accepted method for libraries in future perspective. (6)

Therefore, digital library services through digital library resources are very much accepted method of information service by the modern users.

Objectives:

This paper explains how public libraries adapt to the current situation and what digital services they are providing to their users, and how the impact of digital library services on public libraries has been measured in terms of user satisfaction.

- How and what kinds of digital library service offered by public Libraries.
- What are the impacts of these services on Public Libraries.

Scopes:

Evaluate the importance of each through the interpretation of digital library services and pave the way for their increase in suitability and quantity. This will increase the need for public libraries in line with current improvements.

Methodology:

In order to assess the impact of digital library services, firstly discuss the different types of services and explain their delivery strategies and secondly, explain how appropriate those library services have become as per the needs of the user. An analysis of the two will judge the impact of the Digital Library Service on public libraries.

Detail of Paper:

In the present era, public libraries have improved their repository of information. In line with the so-called hard copy data, there has been an abundance of digital resources that have enabled us to provide digital services. First, a list of digital resources is provided:

S.No	Digital Library Resources
1.	Online Database
2.	OPAC
3.	E-Book
4.	E-Journal
5.	Wireless Network
6.	Search Engine
7.	Local Area Network
8.	Online Newspaper
9.	World Wide Web & Internet
10.	Online index and abstract
11.	CD-ROM
12.	DVD-Rom
13.	Portals
14.	Institutional Repository
15.	Audio Resource
16.	Digital Library
17.	Distant Learning System
18.	Govt. Instant Message Service
19.	Inter Library Loan
20.	Virtual Reference
21.	Ready References
22.	User Technical Support

Table 1: Digital Library Resources

The above mentioned digital library resources are provided through various digital library services. Here is a list:

S.No	Digital Library Services
1.	Information Literacy Services
2.	Online Internet Search Services
3.	Digitization of Local Contents
4.	Electronic Document Delivery Service
5.	E-reference Service
6.	CD-ROM Searching Service
7.	Online Inter Library Service
8.	Technical Training in ICT
9.	Data Management Service
10.	Customer Care Service

11.	Awareness and Workshop Service
12.	Online Cataloging and Classification
13.	E-mail. Service
14.	Data Analysis Service
15.	Audio/Video Conference
16.	Current Awareness Bulletins
17.	Externally Purchased Databases
18.	Bulletin Board Service
19.	Netnews system,
20.	Electronic Table of Contents,
21.	Electronic Theses and Dissertations
22.	Electronic Publishing
23.	Discussion groups and forums
24.	Special Collections service
25.	Remote Information Services

Table 2: Digital Library Services

These digital library services reach the user through the following methods or formats.

- OPAC- The online public access catalog allows all users to search for potentially available documents in a particular library through a computer terminal. It includes various search techniques such as author, title, subject which allows users to search online as a whole and quickly. It helps to show the current status of any document.
- Bibliographic Form- Creating bibliography is one of the most important library work. It shows the brief information of any document such as title, preface, price, abstract author etc.
- Archive- The public library created an archival database containing its various rare documents like- Rare Books, Old Contract Paper, Govt. Contract Paper, Govt. Document, Letters of famous persons which the user can access online via the Internet.
- Literature Search- The public library searches for literature through a variety of national and international data sources, either inside the library or outside the library, by providing CAS, SDI services to its specific users (Academic persons). It is time-centric, transparent and accurate.
- Resource Sharing- Public Libraries shares its own documents with other public libraries through the Inter-Library Loan Service with the help of ICT.
- E-mail Publishing- Necessary news items, short newsletters, articles, etc. are provided to specific users in their e-mail box. This format provides direct connections to users.
- Video Form- Public libraries provide their CD-ROM searching services, audio / video conferencing services in this format. Various academic persons take advantage of this.

Effectiveness of Digital Library Services:

The suitability of Digital Library Services is analyzed to suit the needs of different types of public library users.

- Academician- Individuals associated with the field of education such as teachers, researchers, students take advantage of a variety of e-books, e-journal, ETD, online catalogs, the Internet, the World Wide Web, digital libraries, etc. Updated information helps them with research and learning.
- Officials- Govt. Employees, Private Employees etc take advantage of Govt. instant message service, virtual reference, ready reference, RTI service. These services help them to get different types of Govt. documents.
- Businessman- Different types of business people, management persons, etc. take advantage of various services provided by the public library such as User Technical Support, E-mail, Search Engine, Bulletin Board Service, etc.
- Artist & Performer- These people can avail services like Audio-Video communication, User Technical Support, CD-ROM Database etc.
- Household Persons- They receives services from digital libraries, A-newspapers, current awareness bulletins, etc.

Impact:

Public libraries are affected in many ways by providing digital library services. It is described below.

- Growth and Sustainability- ICT assisted electronic-service delivery makes the service provided much faster and more efficient. As a result, it helps to increase the user's trust and confidence in the service. This has led to an increase in the scope and resources of the public library, which helps the public library to be more lenient with more users.
- Knowledge Enhancement: Users increase their knowledge by acquiring more and updated information. Libraries, on the other hand, have long-standing relationships with users by imposing certain rules or

regulations (Limited access, Password etc) on the provision of such information. As a result, the exchange continues.

- Remote access- With the provision of computerized digital services, it is possible to connect with any user anywhere in the world, at any time, and as a result, the scope of the library has expanded. The library is not confined to just four walls. Again, the amount of user increases which can go national or international level.
- Educational Purpose- The proliferation of national, international level newsletters, E-journals, E-books, E-databases has made public libraries popular with a large number of research persons, academic persons. Has now made the public library public.
- Consortia- Traditional public libraries used to be run exclusively. But now the consortium has been formed through resource sharing. Integration of information has restored unity and stability among public libraries.

Thus, with the current provision of digital or online services, public libraries are being considered as information and documentation centers and are able to make a significant contribution to society.

Conclusion:

Digital library services serve as a source of information for a variety of public library users, helping the user to get information through advanced technology. Users are getting updated information very easily, at the right time, at work or at home. Public libraries, on the other hand, are working together through the formation of consortia and are being promoted nationally or internationally. Above all, public libraries are coming up with new ways to provide human-information services.

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